

3. Article II. Measuring the Audience Experience at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival¹

Bakić, S., Cuenca, J., Cuenca-Amigo, M. (2021). Measuring the Audience Experience at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival. *Event Management Journal* - accepted on January, 12th, 2021

Abstract

Audience research in the cultural sector has been increasingly gaining the attention of researchers and practitioners. This paper explores audience experience as an interactive co-created process between audiences and the program offer in the jazz festival context. As a result of this interaction, each such experience is unique, and the perceived value differs from one to the other. Inspired by previous research on audience experience in the field of theatre performances and musicals, we applied the Art Audience Experience Index to the context of jazz festivals, in this case, a well-established and successful Basque festival: Heineken Jazzaldia, San Sebastián (Spain). The Index measures four indicators: Knowledge, Risk, Authenticity and Collective Engagement. These were utilized to identify co-creation links between festival setting features (paid versus free admission and indoor versus outdoor venue) and audience profiles (education level and music background). The results are obtained from 406 valid questionnaires and reveal the importance audiences give to their live music experience in general, and their satisfaction with jazz concerts in relation to festival concerts' admission, type of venue, participants' educational level and music background. This study contributes to the body of knowledge on audience experience in jazz festivals by employing a tested methodological tool that has not been previously applied in the concert or festival setting. Furthermore, our work may help cultural managers acquaint themselves with their audiences to a greater extent, and incite reflection on interventions that might enhance the experience of their audiences.

Key words: jazz, audiences, Audience Experience Index, co-creation, Heineken Jazzaldia Festival

¹ This paper has been supported by European Commission through Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions under the Deusto International Research School (DIRS-COFUND) project (Grant Agreement number 665959-DIRS-H2020-MSCA-COFUND-2014).

3.1 Introduction

Music audiences (both in concert and festival settings) have been studied from different perspectives and disciplines, and in diverse locations. Literature suggests that socio-psychological factors such as motivation, behavior, barriers and participation in live music events could help organizations orient their marketing and management strategies (Blume-Kohout & Novak-Leonard, 2015; Brown & Knox, 2017; Charron, 2017; Hand & Riley, 2016; Kemp & White, 2013; Lin & Williams, 2014). These factors are also relevant for market, brand and audience segmentation studies at live music events (Barlow & Shibli, 2007; Kruger & Saayman, 2013; Oakes, 2003; Piva et al, 2017; Sigurjonsson, 2010; Tajtakova & Arias-Aranda, 2008), and for the literature on cultural events management (Luonila & Johansson, 2016; Luonila et al., 2016; Tkaczynski, 2014). However, there is a lack of research around co-creation of visitors' experiences in festivals (Van Winkle & Bueddefeld, 2016, Pegg and Patterson, 2010). As Getz (2010) acknowledges, further insights from leisure studies are necessary to enhance understanding of festival experiences.

Drawing from leisure and co-creation studies to generate a theoretical background, this paper explores the experiences of audiences in the jazz festival context by applying the Audience Experience Index as a tested tool to measure the audience experience in the field of performing arts (Radbourne et al., 2009 & Radbourne et al., 2010). The scale has been already tested in drama plays and in one musical (Tung Au et al., 2017), but not in (jazz) concert nor festival settings. For this reason, the well-known Basque festival, Heineken Jazzaldia, in San Sebastián (Spain), was chosen to carry out the fieldwork in July 2019.

The Festival was founded in 1966 and represents one of the oldest jazz festivals in Europe. Almost all world-famous jazz musicians have performed throughout its rich 54-year-old history (heinekenjazzaldia.eus, February 2020). There are sixteen concert venues, both indoor and outdoor, with some charging admission while other performances are free. The main program is held in eight large venues (Trinity Square, Kursaal Auditorium, Victoria Eugenia Theatre, Green Heineken Stage, Heineken Terrace, Frigo Space, Coca-Cola Space and San Telmo Museum-Fundación SGAE Space). Another eight smaller venues are used for the remainder of the program. Previous research on the Heineken Jazzaldia festival (Díez Mintegui & Hernández García, 2010) highlighted the sociability aspect of the festival. Analysis of the Collective Engagement indicator of the Audience Experience Index will bring more insight into this issue.

Specifically, this paper focuses on the audience experience of the 54th edition of Heineken Jazzaldia (Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain) as an interactive co-created process between the audience and the organizational offer in the jazz festival context. Our goal was to explore if and how a methodological tool which evaluates audiences' perceptions of the quality of the performance, the Audience Experience Index (Radbourne et al., 2010), relates to the *festivalscape* setting in terms of the festival's program, facilities and information provided, among others (Grappi & Montanari, 2011; Lee et al. 2008), and to sociodemographic features of the audience such as educational level and music background. We have four specific objectives: (O1) To explore if and how the Audience Experience Index items vary according to the type of admission (free/paid) to the concerts; O2: To explore if and how the Audience Experience Index items vary according to the type of venue (indoor/outdoor) of the concerts; O3: To explore if and how the Audience Experience Index items vary according to the participants' formal education

degree; and O4: To explore if and how the Audience Experience Index items vary given differences in the musical background of the participants (music education or professional/amateur music experience). Finally, the main contribution of this study is the novel implementation of the Audience Experience Index in the festival context, which is understood as an interactive co-created process.

3.2 Theoretical background

To deeply understand the audience experience at a musical, and more generally – cultural event – motivation, behavior, barriers and participation become central. For this line of inquiry, leisure studies offer a relevant theoretical framework.

Stressing the subjective side of leisure, i.e., the notions of “freedom, satisfaction and autotelism” (Cuenca, 2017, p. 32), Cuenca (2017) discusses the consumption of experiences as an emergent experiential paradigm within the framework of liquid modernity set up by Bauman (2000). This observation is in line with the earlier research conducted by Arnould & Price (1993) on the provision of extraordinary experiences (in river rafting trips in the Colorado River basin) that explains how leisure experience emerges only through the subject’s interpretation. Arnould & Price (1993) found that a number of narratives (communion with nature, personal development, interpersonal interaction, belonging to the group) helped participants co-create their extraordinary hedonic experiences.

These insights are particularly relevant for performing arts events, which can be understood both as creative and festive leisure experiences (Cuenca, 2010). They are creative as each audience member, during the reception process, co-creates his or her experience by assigning a certain meaning to the artists’ work. Moreover, performing arts events encompass a festive character as these are extraordinary experiences with

an important social and collective dimension. As typically yearly events, festival experiences may also fit into 'casual leisure' (Stebbins, 1982) which is an "immediately, intrinsically rewarding, relatively short-lived pleasurable activity requiring little or no special training to enjoy it" (Stebbins, 2001, p. 53). Conversely, the concept of 'serious leisure' includes amateurs with different grades of dedication and training in the leisure activity (Stebbins, 2001).

The perspective of leisure studies is strongly coherent with Service-Dominant logic, where consumers are the co-creators of value while organizers facilitate this process (Vargo & Lusch, 2004). From this perspective, co-creation of the service experience happens as a result of interaction among different stakeholders (customers, service providers, etc.), and shapes one's interpretation or reaction to the product (Jaakkola et al., 2015a). The idea from the market perspective that consumers — as *prosumers* — both consume and produce their experiences (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004) refers to cultural audiences as well (Chaney, 2012). In these models, a festival has been explored as a place where the co-creation of experiences takes place.

Recent research on value co-creation conducted by Luonila et al. (2019) suggests festivals' networked productions as a fertile ground for interaction and the exchange of opinions and experiences among festivals' audiences and other agents. Moreover, Werner et al. (2019) identified three types of attendees through value co-creation at sustainable music festivals. Minkiewicz et al. (2014) defend the idea that value derives from the co-created experience. The authors identified three aspects of co-creation in the heritage sector: Co-production, related to customers' participation in the activities and their interaction with the space; Engagement (emotional, intellectual and behavioral) and Personalization, linked to customers choices made during the event

according to their preferences. With the aspect of personalization, attendees can freely move and choose from the abundant festival's program, which is not the case in a single concert setting (Morgan, 2008). Social interactions with friends, families and others shape the visitors' experience at cultural events (Caru & Cova, 2006; Minkiewitz et al., 2014). The festivalscape consists of seven environmental dimensions which are "convenience, staff, information, program content, facilities, souvenirs, and food quality" (Lee et al., 2008, p. 63). The researchers revealed that program content, facilities and food produce emotions and satisfaction in festival attendees. Nevertheless, there is a lack of research on relationship and impact of festivalscape on festival visitor experience (Lee & Chang, 2017).

Jazz audiences have been investigated in a number of ways. Educational research found that conversations with audience members after the concert could help them to understand the artwork and benefit from sharing their jazz interpretations and experience with others (Pitts, 2016; Pitts & Gross, 2017). This way they could identify themselves with other opinions that might differ considerably from musicians' views of jazz performances (Schober & Spiro, 2016). The authors revealed that listeners who had more experience in jazz and in playing the same instrument as the performer were more likely to understand the jazz performance to the same extent the performer did. On the other hand, some listeners with musical background alike, interpreted the jazz improvisations in different ways.

Even though socialization is an important aspect for audiences at a festival (Gelder & Robinson, 2009), the quality of the venues, ticket price and personnel are seen by audiences as some of the most important factors for their jazz festival experience (Williams & Saayman, 2011). However, audiences tend to highlight the quality of the

performance or music shows as the most important factor for their experience (Burland & Pitts, 2010; Linko & Silvanto, 2011; Saleh & Ryan, 1993; Williams & Saayman, 2011). Regarding the festival's venues, there is a lack of research in comparison between outdoor and indoor concert settings. Referring to the co-creation of value in live jazz performances, Oakes & Warnaby (2011) observe a set of potential unpredictable variables that shape visitor experience at outdoor festivals (e.g. weather conditions) and identify lack of research of audience experience in outdoor venues despite their high potential for benefitting marketing experts. Moreover, paid admission concerts at jazz festival are positively correlated with audiences' greater interest in jazz (Thrane, 2002). Previous research on jazz audience profiles showed that jazz attendees generally hold higher formal education qualifications (Oakes, 2003; Oakes, 2010; Saleh & Ryan, 1993). Arts audiences were explored by Kemp (2015) in jazz concerts, among others, analyzing the "Affective, Cognitive, Behavioral, Social and Connection" (2015, p. 182) aspects of the audience that led to identifying features for stronger audience engagements with the arts. Kubacki (2008) drew from interviews with musicians and their perceptions of audiences at jazz concerts. Interestingly, two groups of opinions were formed among the musicians. One considered that, unlike musicians, audiences are not ready to take the risk when listening to a jazz performance. For this group, "the idea of being creative in jazz required the audience to think about what musicians do, be actively engaged in the process of music creation and to be adventurous and prepared for experiments" (2008, p. 406). The second group highlighted the importance of educating the audiences, and that the artists should find some contact point through their own music with audiences.

While previous research on co-creation in events suggests further exploration of the link between audiences' ways of interpreting their experience and festival organization, it is of great importance for academic and practical purposes to acknowledge what aspects are meaningful for audiences' experiences. To explore this, the Audience Experience Index (Radbourne et al., 2009; Radbourne et al., 2010) was chosen as a tool that offers fruitful insights into the audience experience, yet it has not been previously implemented in the concert/festival setting. The following section describes the methodological process and adaptation of the tool to the jazz festival context.

3.3 Methods

3.3.1 Instrument

The Audience Experience Index consists of four indicators: Knowledge, Authenticity, Risk and Collective Engagement. Each indicator is measured by four items, so that the entire Index comprises a total of 16 items. Half of them (two items of each category) assess the importance the interviewee gives to the performing arts shows in general (Importance dimension), and the rest captures satisfaction with the previously attended show (Satisfaction dimension). 'Knowledge' concerns the cognitive stimulation provided by the artistic work and the level of information about the work necessary to fulfil the audiences' intellectual goals. 'Risk' describes the probability of repeated attendance according to factors such as familiarity with the place or arts centre where the show is being held and readiness to pay for the show, which goes along with economic risk. Furthermore, 'Risk' evaluates satisfaction with the logistics of the performance (parking, ticket, personnel, transport), as well as the personal emotional risk related to the level of enthusiasm created by the performance. 'Authenticity' includes an emotional component on the one hand, and expectations regarding the artists' representation of

the work on the other. 'Collective engagement' concerns the relationships audiences create with the performance and other audience members during and after the show. Besides the two dimensions (Importance and Satisfaction) and the indicators (Knowledge, Risk, Authenticity and Collective Engagement), Radbourne et al. (2010) proposed a set of items related to the participants' familiarity with the venue/artists/performing art shows and their grade of motivation for attendance. All four indicators of the Audience Experience Index influence perception of the quality of an artistic work (Radbourne et al., 2010). A pilot project carried out by Radbourne et al. (2010) demonstrated that if these four indicators are met, there is greater probability that the attendance will be repeated.

We thus adapted the Index and survey to the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival context, which was verified by two external experts. First, suggestions made by the co-author of the Index were taken into account. Then the other expert reviewed the survey and contributed additional observations. The adapted version of the questionnaire was translated into Spanish and piloted through a pretest in the Getxo Jazz festival from the 2nd until the 5th of July, 2019. 100 questionnaires were distributed in total and 87 were filled out in this phase. The pretest served to indicate the audience's understanding of the Index, and, as a consequence, certain modifications were made to the questionnaire for its definitive administration during the Heineken Jazzaldia festival. After the pretest, two additional researchers were asked to review the adapted Spanish version of the questionnaire for the Heineken Jazzaldia festival: a researcher who is familiar with the cultural background of the music festival context and a professor with linguistic background in both Spanish and English. Accordingly, the tool underwent several linguistic changes. As an alternative to the backward translation, suggestions made by

Douglas and Craig (2006) were taken into account in terms of the collaborative and iterative translation conducted among the authors of this article (who had previous translation experience from English to Spanish and vice versa), experts' consultation, pretesting and audience feedback regarding the understanding of the Index prior to its final distribution at Heineken Jazzaldia festival.

The final version prepared for Heineken Jazzaldia included several types of modifications in comparison with the original version of the Index. First, respondents were asked for the name of the concert they had just attended. This information enabled the research team to identify the concert's type of admission (paid versus free) and the type of venue (indoor versus outdoor). Second, a 1 to 5 point Likert scale (e. g. Totally disagree – Totally agree) was included for each item and an additional 'Do not know/Does not apply' field added. Greater modifications were applied in the Familiarity group of items. The original version consists of 8 items while the Festival's had 10. Lexical adaptations involved replacing words such as "performance" or "venue" with "concert" and "festival" where appropriate. The item from the original version, that "I really like the work of this particular playwright/composer/choreographer," was excluded while three new items were included. To clarify these differences, Table 1. shows the final version followed by the original one from the Index. The items of the Heineken Jazzaldia questionnaire are translated into English for the purposes of the article. Only the Spanish version was distributed during the Festival.

Table 1. Familiarity group of items

Questionnaire Heineken Jazzaldia 2019	Original Audience Experience Index
F1. I attend as many performances at Heineken Jazzaldia festival as possible.	<i>* I attend as many performances at this venue as possible.</i>
F2. I really like the selection of artists at this festival.	
F3. I really like the selection of artists at this venue (stage).	
F4. I really like the work of this particular musician/musical group.	<i>* I really like the work of this particular company/orchestra.</i>
F5. I really like how the Festival is being organized.	
F6. I really like this type of music festival.	<i>* I really like this type of performing arts (theatre , music, dance).</i>
F7. I would like to go to this type of music festival more often.	<i>* I would like to go to this type of performance more often.</i>
F8. I have been looking forward to coming to this music festival.	<i>* I have been looking forward to coming to this performance.</i>
F9. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of friends and /or family.	<i>* I have been looking forward to watching this performance in the company of friends and /or family.</i>
F10. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of other people who are interested in this type of music.	<i>* I have been looking forward to watching this performance in the company of other people who are interested in the work.</i>

Regarding the whole survey, as the English language is more gender neutral than Spanish, words like “artists” or “performers” were replaced by both masculine and feminine Spanish words. Concerning the Importance dimension (Table 2), participants were asked to fill in this part of the survey bearing in mind their attendance at music events in general including other types of musical performances they attended prior to this festival. Greater changes concern two items from the Satisfaction group of items (Table 2). The Knowledge item from Satisfaction dimension (Table 2, S4) was modified to enhance understanding of the jazz context instead of the original version “My enjoyment or appreciation increased because I understood the meaning of the production.” The Risk item from Satisfaction dimension (Table 2, S7) replaced the original “I felt tense and excited at moments during the performance,” as advised by the language experts.

Table 2. Questionnaire Heineken Jazzaldia 2019: Importance and Satisfaction dimensions

Importance		
Knowledge	I1.	Notes about the performance and the work of the artists are included in the program.
Risk	I2.	The venue/arts centre/festival presents my preferred type of shows.
Authenticity	I3.	The performance matches expectations from the promotional description.
Collective Engagement	I4.	Audiences know there are established rules for audience behavior (eg. When to clap, no speaking during the concert).
Authenticity	I5.	The musicians/musical groups show technical skill and understanding of the work.
Risk	I6.	I have previously seen or heard this work (production), or accessed a preview on the Web.
Knowledge	I7.	When I attend a concert I want to be challenged to think differently about ideas and issues presented in the show.
Collective Engagement	I8.	Audience members have the opportunity to discuss the performance with others some time after the show.
Satisfaction		
Risk	S1.	The quality of the concert was worth the cost of attendance (ticket, transport, parking, personal).
Authenticity	S2.	The reputation of the performers was matched by the quality of the performance.
Knowledge	S3.	I learned something new from this performance.
Knowledge	S4.	My enjoyment or appreciation of Jazz increased from this performance.
Authenticity	S5.	The best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience.
Collective Engagement	S6.	Other members of the audience seemed to have a similar response to the performance as I did.
Risk	S7.	I felt enthusiastic and excited at moments during the concert.
Collective Engagement	S8.	Attending this live performance with other people increased my understanding of how audiences and performers interact.

The Familiarity group of items and the four indicators for Knowledge, Authenticity, Risk and Collective Engagement from the Importance and Satisfaction dimensions were followed by sociodemographic questions. Age, occupation, gender and the highest formal education degree obtained (adapted to the Spanish educational system) were included as in Radbourne et al. (2009), and two additional questions were introduced regarding the music education or professional/amateur music experiences of the respondents, as well as participants' current residence area. An additional change regarding gender was incorporated adding the "other denomination" option beside "male" and "female".

3.3.2 Sample

Convenience sampling was applied while making sure to include both genders and various age groups. When dealing with unknown population proportions, a conservative response format is recommended to determine a sample size, meaning that 50 percent of the population has a positive opinion, and 50 percent negative about any question

(Aaker & Day, 2019; Akis et al, 1996). We have selected 5 percent sampling error and 95 percent confidence level.

This is a cross-sectional design. The size of the sample determines the error as the calculation of the sample size is independent of the total population size (Aaker & Day, 2019). The researchers reached 431 participants. As it was not possible to control if participants filled the whole questionnaire out during the fieldwork, there is missing data. Moreover, a 'Do not know/Does not apply' field was considered missing data as well. A total 25 questionnaires had more than 30% of missing data (fields left in blank). These were considered not valid and excluded from the sample. The sample covers 406 valid filled out surveys from 29 concerts throughout the whole duration of the Festival. As Shipway et al. (2012) stress, it is of high importance to carry out the fieldwork each day of the event to ensure both local participants and the ones from outside the region are represented in the sample due to increased attendance during the weekends by the non-local people. The authors also consider convenience sampling as one of the most frequent methods used when it comes to audiences' motivation and satisfaction at events.

As this research is of exploratory nature, the findings are considered significant to take into consideration. The statistical error is 4.8 percent for the sample population. The statistical significance has the 0.05 level of confidence. For this procedure, see data sample determination in Pappas (2017). The classification variables with missing data are presented in the Table 3.

Table 3. Classification variables

Classification variables	Number of participants	% Sample participants
Gender		
Male	182	45.5
Female	209	52.3
Other denomination	7	1.8
Missing data	6	
Age Group		
Under 30	65	16.3
31 to 40	67	16.8
41 to 50	111	27.8
51 to 60	103	25.8
61+	54	13.5
Missing data	6	
Occupation		
Employed	304	76.2
Student	29	7.3
Retired	40	10.0
Other	20	5.0
Working and studying	4	1.0
Missing data	7	
Education		
-highest degree obtained-		
Primary school	14	3.5
Secondary school	65	16.3
Bachelor degree	219	54.8
Master or PhD degree	102	25.5
Missing data	6	
Music background		
Music education	78*	19.7
Professional/Amateur music experience	124**	31.4
Neither music education nor professional/amateur music experience	193	48.9
Missing data	11	
Residence area		
San Sebastián	119	29.8
Guipúzkoa (outside of San Sebastián)	40	10.0
Bizkaia and Álava (Basque Country outside of Guipúzkoa)	35	8.8
Spain (outside the Basque Country)	177	44.3
Outside of Spain	29	7.2
Missing data	6	
Admission		
Paid admission to concerts	213	54.3
Free admission to concerts	179	45.7
Missing data	14	
Type of venue		
Indoor venue concerts	307	78.3
Outdoor venue concerts	85	21.7
Missing data	14	

*51 participants hold music education, and 27 have additional professional or amateur music experience beside music education

** 97 participants have amateur music experience, 25 professional music experience and 2 people both professional and amateur music experience

As reflected in the table, there were no participants who did not have any degree of education. Regarding their music backgrounds, participants are split into three groups. The first group contains 78 respondents who claimed to have music education, of which 27 also have professional or amateur music experience. In the analysis this group will be called 'Music education'. The total number of participants for this aspect is 395 as 11 people did not respond to this question. Regarding the type of venue, a total of 14 respondents did not highlight which concert they attended. Therefore, it is not known whether these participants attended an indoor/outdoor venue or had a paid/free admission.

3.3.3 Data collection and analysis

Questionnaires were distributed throughout the five days of the festival (24-28 July, 2019), at both the indoor and outdoor venues. Six researchers equipped with questionnaires, folders and pencils administered the surveys. The stages used for distribution were Heineken Terrace, Green Heineken Stage, Frigo Space, Coca-Cola Space in the open air, and Kursaal Auditorium, Victoria Eugenia Theatre and Victoria Eugenia Club (which is inside of the Victoria Eugenia Theatre). The San Telmo Museum-Fundación SGAE Space was also used for distribution. This stage is inside the museum building, in a small open space under a concert tent. As it differs considerably from the outdoor venues used for distribution – which are on the beach or just nearby where many visitors pass by – the concerts held at the San Telmo Museum stage were analyzed as indoor venue concerts. All the venues used for distribution of the questionnaires are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Heineken Jazzaldia venues used for distribution of the questionnaires: no. 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 13

Adapted from Heineken Jazzaldia 2019 program: <https://heinekenjazzaldia.eus/en/>

One of the limitations of the fieldwork was the weather conditions, as it rained on the 25th, 26th and 27th, which is why some concerts on the beach could not be used for the sample. Moreover, some concerts were cancelled. Nevertheless, the porch roof sections in front of the indoor venues were used for distribution. Another limitation was the late night hours of the concerts. As visibility was diminished, surveys could only be distributed until approximately 9 pm. Data were analyzed using the IBM SPSS Statistics 26. The Independent T-test and One-way Anova were carried out for the analysis. The following section include the results, which are reported as suggested by Field (2013).

3.4 Results

Tables 4. & 5. include both statistically significant and non-significant differences obtained during the analysis for the Knowledge, Authenticity, Risk and Collective Engagement indicators (from both the Importance and Satisfaction dimensions) and the items from the Familiarity group of items, according to our four objectives.

Table 4. Familiarity group of items: significant and non-significant differences according to the four defined objectives

	Indepent T tests				One way ANOVA			
	O1: Admission(paid/free)		O2: Type of venue (indoor/outdoor)		O3: Education		O4: Music background	
	t(df)	p-value	t(df)	p-value	F(df)	p-value	F(df)	p-value
F1. I attend as many performances at Heineken Jazzaldia festival as possible.	t(384)=-0,436	0,663	T(384)=0,826	0,409	F(3,390)=0,513	0,674	F(2,386)= 0,423	0,655
F2. I really like the selection of artists at this Festival.	t(385)=1,910	0,057	T(385)=2,312	0,021*	F(3,391)= 1,167	0,322	F(2,387)= 0,918	0,400
F3. I really like the selection of artists at this venue (stage).	t(374)=1,870	0,062	T(110,070)=2,412	0,018*	F(3,379)= 0,976	0,404	F(2,375)= 0,622	0,538
F4. I really like the work of this particular musician/musical group.	t(375)=1,140	0,255	T(375)=2,249	0,025*	F(3,381)=1,078	0,358	F(2,377)= 0,525	0,592
F5. I really like how the Festival is being organized.	t(385)=0,559	0,577	T(385)=0,940	0,348	F(3,391)=0,313	0,816	F(2,387)= 1,694	0,185
F6. I really like this type of music festivals.	t(388)=-0,917	0,359	T(388)=0,611	0,542	F(3,394)=3,566	0,014*	F(2,390)=1,159	0,315
F7. I would like to go to this type of music festivals more often.	t(386)=-0,368	0,713	T(386)=0,811	0,418	F(3,391)=2,124	0,097	F(2,387)= 0,878	0,416
F8. I have been looking forward to coming to this music festival.	t(307,057)=1,657	0,099	T(379)=2,651	0,008*	F(3,385)=1,359	0,255	F(2,381)= 1,428	0,241
F9. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of friends and /or family.	t(380)=0,386	0,700	T(380)=1,318	0,188	F(3,385)=0,966	0,409	F(2,381)= 0,885	0,414
F10. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of other people who are interested in this type of music.	t(372)=1,925	0,055	T(110,704)=3,351	0,001*	F(3,377)=0,795	0,497	F(2,373)= 0,633	0,531

Note. *p<.0.05

Table 5. Importance and Satisfaction group of items: significant and non-significant differences according to the four defined objectives

I1. Notes about the performance and the work of the artists are included in the program.	t(381)=-1,002	0,317	T(381)=-0,075	0,940	F(3,387)=2,811	0,039*	F(2,384)= 0,415	0,661
I2. The venue/arts centre/festival presents my preferred type of shows.	t(377)=0,503	0,616	T(377)=0,145	0,885	F(3,382)=0,313	0,816	F(2,378)= 0,571	0,565
I3. The performance matches expectations from the promotional description.	t(376)=-0,109	0,913	T(376)=-0,444	0,657	F(3,382)=1,631	0,182	F(2,378)= 0,591	0,554
I4. Audiences know there are established rules for audience behavior (eg. When to clap, no speaking during the concert).	t(375)=0,926	0,355	T(375)=2,204	0,028*	F(3,381)=0,812	0,488	F(2,377)= 0,894	0,41
I5. The musicians/musical groups show technical skill and understanding of the work.	t(381)=1,438	0,151	T(381)=-0,560	0,576	F(3,386)=0,210	0,890	F(2,382)= 2,256	0,106
I6. I have previously seen or heard this work (production), or accessed a preview on the Web.	t(323,847)=2,710	0,007*	T(353)=2,030	0,043*	F(3,358)=0,131	0,941	F(2,356)= 0,216	0,806
I7. When I attend a concert I want to be challenged to think differently about ideas and issues presented in the show.	t(371)=1,460	0,145	T(371)=2,380	0,018*	F(3,375)=1,990	0,115	F(2,371)= 1,775	0,171
I8. Audience members have the opportunity to discuss the performance with others some time after the show.	t(363)=1,155	0,249	T(363)=2,459	0,014*	F(3,368)=0,978	0,403	F(2,365)= 0,289	0,749
S1. The quality of the concert was worth the cost of attendance (ticket, transport, parking, personal).	t(368)=-0,970	0,333	T(368)=-0,469	0,640	F(3,373)=5,210	0,002*	F(2,369)= 0,058	0,943
S2. The reputation of the performers was matched by the quality of the performance.	t(363)=2,057	0,040*	T(363)=2,129	0,034*	F(3,369)=0,829	0,478	F(2,365)= 0,155	0,857
S3. I learned something new from this performance.	t(378)=2,682	0,008*	T(378)=5,891	0,000**	F(3,383)=2,534	0,057	F(2,379)= 1,615	0,200
S4. My enjoyment or appreciation of Jazz increased from this performance.	t(373)=-0,783	0,434	T(373)=0,521	0,603	F(3,378)=0,116	0,951	F(2,374)= 5,356	0,005*
S5. The best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience.	t(359,660)=-2,825	0,005*	T(364)=-1,996	0,047*	F(3,370)=1,305	0,273	F(2,366)= 0,397	0,672
S6. Other members of the audience seemed to have a similar response to the performance as I did.	t(357)=-1,171	0,242	T(357)=-0,359	0,720	F(3,363)=0,344	0,793	F(2,359)= 0,676	0,509
S7. I felt enthusiastic and excited at moments during the concert.	t(388)=-0,221	0,825	T(388)=2,955	0,003*	F(3,394)=1,165	0,323	F(2,390)= 7,783	0,000**
S8. Attending this live performance with other people increased my understanding of how audiences and performers interact.	t(370)=-0,518	0,605	T(370)=-0,062	0,950	F(3,375)=0,239	0,869	F(2,371)= 2,96	0,053

*Note. *p<0.05 **p<0.001*

The following sections report only on significant differences according to our four objectives. Each result refers to the items from the Familiarity group of items and the Knowledge, Authenticity, Risk and Collective Engagement indicators (from both the Importance and Satisfaction dimensions) of the questionnaire (Tables 1 & 2). Each result

is preceded by the items' identification letter/number from the Familiarity (F), Importance (I) and Satisfaction (S) groups of the questionnaire (Tables 1 & 2).

3.4.1 Type of admission (free/paid) to the concerts

In order to explore if and how each item of the Audience Experience Index varies according to the type of admission (free/paid) to the concerts, a series of Independent T-Tests were carried out, one for each item. This section reports on the significant differences between survey participants who paid and those who attended the concert for free. In summary, these stem from the following indicator (dimension) groups: Risk (Importance), Authenticity (Satisfaction), and Knowledge (Satisfaction).

➤ Risk (Importance)

I6. On average, participants who paid admission to the concert ascribed more importance to seeing or hearing about the work (production) or accessing a preview online before live music events in general ($M=3.72$, $SE=0.07$) than participants who attended a free admission concert ($M=3.41$, $SE=0.09$). Based on $n=355$, this difference, 0.32, 95% CI [0.09, 0.55] is significant, $t(323.85)=2.71$, $p=0.007$.

➤ Authenticity (Satisfaction)

S2. The participants who paid for the concert ticket were satisfied to a greater extent with the match between the reputation of the performers and the quality of the performance they attended at the festival ($M=4.47$, $SE=0.54$) than participants who attended a free admission concert ($M=4.29$, $SE=0.67$). Based on $n=365$, this difference, 0.17, 95% CI [0.00, 0.34] is significant $t(363)=2.06$, $p=0.04$.

S5. Conversely, the ones who attended the concert for free agreed to a greater extent that the best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience ($M=4.04$, $SE=0.73$) than participants who paid admission to the concert ($M=3.74$,

SE=0.72). Based on $n=366$, this difference, -0.29 , 95% CI $[-0.49, -0.09]$ is significant $t(359.66)=-2.80$, $p=0.005$.

➤ Knowledge (Satisfaction)

S3. On average, participants who paid admission to the concert reported to have learnt something new from the concert to a greater extent ($M=4.32$, $SE=0.52$) than participants who attended free admission concert ($M=4.09$, $SE=0.67$). Based on $n=380$, this difference, 0.23 , 95% CI $[0.06, 0.40]$ is significant $t(378)=2.68$, $p=0.008$.

3.4.2 Type of venue (indoor/outdoor) of the concerts

To explore if and how each item of the Audience Experience Index varies according to the type of venue (indoor/outdoor) of the concerts, another series of Independent T-Tests were carried out, one for each item. This section reports on the significant differences between participants of the survey who attended concerts in indoor and outdoor venues, and these differences refer to the items from the Familiarity dimension as well as the items related to indicators Collective Engagement, Risk and Knowledge (Importance dimension), and Authenticity, Knowledge, and Risk (Satisfaction dimension).

➤ Familiarity

Regarding this group of items, participants who attended an indoor venue concert, on average, showed higher agreement than the ones who attended the outdoor venue concert:

F2. Indoor concert attendees liked the selection of artists at the Festival to a greater extent ($M=3.93$, $SE=0.46$) than participants who attended an outdoor venue concert

(M=3.70, SE=0.96). Based on n=387, this difference, 0.23, 95% CI [0.03, 0.43] is significant $t(385)=2.31$, $p=0.021$.

F3. They also liked the selection of artists at the specific venue more (M=4.08, SE=0.46) than the outdoor venue concert participants (M=3.79, SE=0.11), based on n=376, with significant difference, 0.29, 95% CI [0.05, 0.53], $t(110.07)=2.41$, $p=0.018$.

F4. They liked the work of the musician/musical group more (M=4.22, SE=0.56) than the outdoor venue ones (M=3.93, SE=0.11), based on n=377, with significant difference, 0.28, 95% CI [0.03, 0.53], $t(375)=2.25$, $p=0.025$.

F8. They were looking forward to a greater extent to coming to this music festival (M=4.44, SE=0.44) than did the ones in the outdoor venue (M=4.18, SE=0.98), based on n=381, with significant difference 0.26, 95% CI [0.07, 0.46], $t(379)=2.651$, $p=0.008$.

F10. Finally, the indoor venue concert participants were looking forward to being accompanied by other people interested in that type of music at the festival (M=4.20, SE=0.52) more than were the outdoor venue concert participants (M=3.77, SE=0.11). Based on n=374, this difference, 0.43, 95% CI [0.17, 0.68] is significant $t(110.70)=3.35$, $p=0.001$.

➤ **Collective Engagement (Importance)**

I4. On average, participants who attended the indoor venue concert ascribed more importance to audience behavior rules (to know when to clap, or not to speak during the concert) at live music events in general (M=4.30, SE=0.45) than participants who attended outdoor venue concerts (M=4.07, SE=0.10). Based on n=377, this difference, 0.22, 95% CI [0.02,0.43] is significant $t(375)=2.20$, $p=0.028$.

I8. They also ascribed greater importance to having the opportunity to discuss the performance with others some time after the show at the live music events in general

($M=3.37$, $SE=0.58$) than the outdoor venue ones ($M=3.06$, $SE=0.11$). Based on $n=365$, this difference is significant, 0.30 , 95% CI [$0.06,0.55$], $t(363)=2.46$, $p=0.014$.

➤ Risk (Importance)

I6. Greater importance to seeing or hearing about the work (production) or accessing a preview online before live music events in general is ascribed by the indoor venue concert participants ($M=3.64$, $SE=0.65$) than the outdoor venue ones ($M=3.35$, $SE=0.13$). Based on $n=355$, this difference is significant, 0.29 , 95% CI [$0.00,0.57$], $t(353)=2.03$, $p=0.043$.

➤ Knowledge (Importance)

I7. On average, the indoor venue concert participants ascribed more importance to being challenged to think differently about ideas and issues presented in the show at the live music events in general ($M=3.95$, $SE=0.52$) than the outdoor venue ones ($M=3.69$, $SE=0.93$). Based on $n=373$, this difference, 0.26 , 95% CI [$0.046,0.48$] is significant $t(371)=2.38$, $p=0.018$.

➤ Authenticity (Satisfaction)

S2. On average, participants who attended an indoor venue concert were satisfied to a greater extent with the match between the reputation of the performers and the quality of the performance they attended at the festival ($M=4.44$, $SE=0.48$) than participants who attended outdoor venue concerts ($M=4.22$, $SE=0.91$). Based on $n=365$, this difference, 0.22 , 95% CI [$0.02, 0.43$] is significant $t(363)=2.13$, $p=0.034$.

S5. On the other hand, on average, participants who attended outdoor venue concerts considered that the best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience ($M=4.08$, $SE=0.11$) to a greater extent than participants who attended an

indoor venue concert (M=3.82, SE=0.59). Based on n=366, this difference, -0.25, 95% CI [-0.50, -0.00] is significant $t(364)=-2$, $p=0.047$.

➤ Knowledge (Satisfaction)

S3. On average, participants who attended indoor venue concerts reported that they learned something new from the concert to a greater extent (M=4.34, SE=0.44) than participants who attended outdoor venue concerts (M=3.74, SE=0.10). Based on n=380, this difference, 0.60, 95% CI [0.40, 0.80] is significant $t(378)=5.89$, $p=0.000$.

➤ Risk (Satisfaction)

S7. On average, participants who attended indoor venue concerts reported having felt enthusiastic and excited at moments during the concert (M=4.33, SE=0.49) to a greater extent than participants who attended outdoor venue concerts (M=4.01, SE=0.99). Based on n=390, this difference, 0.31, 95% CI [0.10, 0.52] is significant $t(388)=2.95$, $p=0.003$.

3.4.3 Formal education qualifications of the participants

One-way Anova tests were applied to explore if and how each item of the Audience Experience Index varies according to the highest formal education degree obtained. The following section reports on significant differences between the participants' formal education degrees (Primary School, Secondary School, Bachelor's and Master or PhD degree) and each item. The post hoc tests identified that the significant relationships are Familiarity, Knowledge (Importance) and Risk (Satisfaction).

➤ Familiarity

F6. There are significant differences between participants with different highest formal education degrees obtained, in terms of the extent to which they like this type of music

festival, $F(3,394)=3,566$, $p=0,014$, based on $n=398$. The post hoc tests showed that the participants who preferred this type of music festival were the ones who hold a Bachelor degree ($M=4.55$, $SE=0.04$) and Master or PhD degree ($M=4.67$, $SE=0.64$), in comparison with the participants with Secondary School qualifications ($M=4.31$, $SE=0.11$).

➤ Knowledge (Importance)

I1. A significant relationship also exists between different highest formal education degrees and notes about the performance and artist's work in the program at live music events in general, $F(3,387)=2,811$, $p=0,039$, based on $n=391$. The post hoc test revealed that Secondary School participants found this aspect less important to their experience ($M=4.16$, $SE=0.10$) than participants with Primary School education ($M=4.69$, $SE=0.13$) and those with a Bachelor's degree ($M=4.39$, $SE=0.05$).

➤ Risk (Satisfaction)

S1. Significant differences are identified between different highest levels of education and whether the quality of the concert was worth the cost of attendance in terms of ticket, transport, parking and personal, $F(3,373)=5,210$, $p=0,002$, based on $n=377$. According to the post hoc test, the Secondary School participants were less satisfied with this aspect ($M=3.96$, $SE=0.15$) compared to the Bachelor ($M=4.43$, $SE=0.05$) and Master or PhD degree respondents ($M=4.44$, $SE=0.08$).

3.4.4 Musical background of the participants

One-way ANOVA tests were carried out to explore if and how each item of the Audience Experience Index varies given differences in the musical background of the participants (education, professional/amateur experiences and none of the two). The post hoc tests identified that the significant relationship is in Risk and Knowledge (Satisfaction).

➤ Risk (Satisfaction)

S7. A significant difference is identified between the participants with Professional/Amateur music experience, who felt more enthusiastic and excited during the concert they attended ($M=4.51, SE=0.06$) than ones with Music education ($M=4.11, SE=0.11$) and ones with neither music education nor experience ($M=4.15, SE=0.06$), $F(2,390)=7,783, p=0,000$, based on $n=393$.

➤ Knowledge (Satisfaction)

S4. A significant relationship lies between the Music education respondents whose enjoyment or appreciation of Jazz was less increased from the performance they attended ($M=3.33, SE=0.13$) in comparison with the Professional/Amateur music experience respondents ($M=3.80, SE=0.09$) and ones with neither music education nor experience ($M=3.73, SE=0.07$), $F(2,374)=5,356, p=0,005$, based on $n=377$.

3.5 Discussion

This research offers insights into the relationship between aspects of co-creation among jazz festival attendees' experience through four indicators of the Audience Experience Index (Radbourne et al., 2009; Radbourne et al., 2010) – Knowledge, Risk, Authenticity and Collective Engagement – the participants' familiarity with the festival setting, and motivation for their attendance across a set of objectives: admission (free versus paid) to concerts, the type of venue (indoor versus outdoor) of the concerts, the highest formal qualifications and the musical background of the participants. The following discusses the obtained results through four indicators (Radbourne et al., 2009) and prior familiarity with a festival/venue/musicians and a summary is provided regarding the four objectives of the research and their interrelationship across items where applicable.

Regarding the Risk indicator, participants who paid admission to the concert indicated managing less risk as they ascribed more importance to seeing or hearing about the work (production), or accessing a preview online, before the concert at live music events in general than participants who attended the concert for free. The indoor venue concert participants also ascribed more importance to risk than participants who attended the outdoor venue concerts. This preparation for the concert could be related with the audiences' engagement with a performance, which could help realize the co-creation process as understood by Minkiewitz et al. (2014). As Williams & Saayman (2011) assure, ticket price is one of the most important factors for jazz audience experience. Bearing in mind that jazz attendees predominantly hold higher educational degrees (Oakes, 2003; Oakes, 2010; Saleh & Ryan, 1993), this study compared different audiences' degree levels with their concert experience. Our research shows that participants with Secondary school qualifications were less satisfied concerning the cost of attendance (ticket, transport, parking and personal) in relation to the quality of the concert attended than the ones with Bachelor and Master/PhD degree. Therefore, they experienced higher financial risk.

Concerning engagement as part of the co-creation process (Minkiewitz et al. 2014), its emotional component is revealed in another aspect of the Risk indicator, as the indoor venue concert participants reported experiencing more enthusiastic and exciting moments during the performance than the outdoor venue ones. Similarly, participants with Professional or Amateur music experience felt more enthusiastic and excited at moments during the concert than the ones with Music education. In addition, the latter experienced less enjoyment or appreciation of jazz from the concert in comparison with participants with Professional and Amateur music experience. This is related to the

Knowledge indicator that describes cognitive growth as well as personal development. Participants who consider themselves music professionals or amateurs reported higher emotional and cognitive engagement with the performance, which goes in line with serious leisure activity (Stebbins, 2001) that helps understanding of the artwork and, therefore, enhances listeners' music experience at this casual leisure event. On the other side, participants with music education have had somewhat different criteria for their jazz enjoyment and learning in comparison with professional and amateur musicians. While research conducted by Schober & Spiro (2016) recognizes possibilities of highly different interpretations of recorded live jazz performances among listeners with similar music background, this study showed that participants who hold music education extracted less learning and enjoyment than professional and amateur musicians with no music education background in the live jazz setting. Consequently, the latter were more engaged in the performance, which is a desirable response from the audience for some musicians in terms of openness and willingness to listen to jazz (Kubacki, 2008).

Participants who attended paid admission concerts reported a higher level of cognitive stimulation from the performance, as they claimed to have learnt something new from the jazz concert to a greater extent than the free admission concert attendees. The intellectual stimulation derived from the concert was also higher in the indoor venue concert participants than the outdoor venue ones. Moreover, Primary and Bachelor's degree visitors gave more importance to being informed about the concert through the program at live music events in general than did Secondary School participants. This cognitive component forms part of the co-creation and creative experiences as audience members extracted meaning from what they had listened and learnt (Cuenca, 2010).

Regarding the Authenticity indicator in terms of the match between the reputation of the performers and the quality of the performance, participants who paid admission for the concert were satisfied to a greater extent with this aspect than participants with free admission. The same applies for the ones who attended an indoor venue concert, whose expectations were met to a higher extent regarding this match than the outdoor venue concert participants. However, those who attended free admission concerts agreed to a greater extent than the paid admission concert participants that the best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience. This also applies to the outdoor venue concert participants whose experiences reflected greater importance of a direct relationship with the musicians than the indoor venue participants. These results from the Authenticity indicator show participants' expectations met toward the performance, including the relationship between the performers and the audience. Interaction among different actors facilitates co-creation of experience and impacts the interpretation of the cultural product (Jaakkola et al., 2015a), in this case a jazz concert. This does not mean the indoor venue participants and the ones with the paid admission did not experience interaction. It may be that musicians' direct communication with the audience was less relevant for their interpretation of the performance, and therefore, experience.

When it comes to familiarity with the festival context, participants with Bachelor, Master and PhD degree reported liking to a greater extent this type of music festival than the ones with Secondary School. In general, indoor venue concert participants reported higher agreement in the Familiarity group of items regarding motivation for festival attendance and being accompanied by other people at the festival, the extent to which they liked this type of music festival, the selection of artists at the specific venue at the

Festival, and the work of the musical group than the outdoor venue concert participants. The indoor venue concert participants ascribed more importance to the Collective Engagement indicator when it comes to audience behavior rules and opportunity to discuss about the concert with others afterwards at live music events in general than the outdoor venue concert participants. The latter is important for interaction and sharing of experiences at live performances (Radbourne et al., 2009; Radbourne et al., 2010). This interaction among audience members could help their interpretation of the performance (Pitts, 2016; Pitts & Gross, 2017) and facilitate the co-creation process of their experiences (Jaakkola et al., 2015a). The result that audience behavior rules gained greater importance by the indoor venue participants, could lead to the conclusion that if these expectations are not met, disruption of experience might take place.

Finally, according to our first two objectives (paid versus free admission to concerts and indoor versus outdoor concert venues), the results have shown that participants who paid for the concert ticket, along with the ones who attended an indoor venue concert had higher rates of agreement according to Knowledge, Risk and Authenticity in comparison with free admission and outdoor venue concert participants. Consequently, they had higher cognitive stimulation and learning from the jazz concert, and showed greater satisfaction in terms of expectations they had about performers' reputation and the quality of the performance. Moreover, they prefer to risk less and inform themselves about the artwork before going to concerts. On the contrary, the participants who attended free admission concerts, as well as those who attended outdoor venue concerts, agreed to a greater extent that the best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience, which shows their engagement with performers positively related to satisfactory and meaningful experiences. Besides,

indoor venue participants showed higher need to be intellectually challenged, greater emotional impact provoked by performance and gave more importance to audience behavior rules and the opportunity to discuss about the performance with others after the concert than the outdoor venue ones. A tentative explanation for this may be the environmental features of the festivalscape outdoors that influence and additionally accompany audience experience (e.g. food, landscape, weather conditions, crowds) whereas the intimacy of the indoor venues has fewer distractions and allows the audience member to predominantly focus on the performance. These insights hopefully contribute to the body of knowledge and fill to some extent the gap identified by academics in search of additional answers on how the experiences are co-created in the festival setting (Getz, 2012; Lee & Chang, 2017; Oakes & Warnaby, 2011; Pegg and Patterson, 2010; Van Winkle & Bueddefeld, 2016).

3.6 Managerial implications

This research explored the indicators from the Audience Experience Index (Radbourne et al., 2010) within the jazz festival context. Taking into account the significant differences extracted from the results, they may offer an insight to jazz festival managers and marketing experts when it comes to the importance audiences attribute to knowledge, expectations and engagement within the jazz festival setting. As festival attendees can freely choose the concerts they want to attend within a festival (Morgan, 2008), this research is aimed to reflect to a certain extent the aspects that influence the experience of specific groups of participants in the jazz festival context. As Thrane (2002) advised, greater jazz lovers tend to spend more money at the festival. From our results, paid admission attendees did report greater learning and intellectual stimulation from the concerts and higher interest in being informed on the musicians' work prior to the

concert than free admission concert attendees. They also showed higher expectations from the concert and higher satisfaction regarding the quality of the performance and artists' reputation. Moreover, indoor venue concert participants enjoyed being intellectually and emotionally engaged in the concert and liked opportunities to discuss about the performance after the concert to a greater extent than the outdoor venue attendees. They also placed greater importance on audience behavior rules such as clapping and silence during the concert. The outdoor venue participants rated the musicians' direct communication with audience more beneficial for their experience than the indoor venue ones. Audiences with professional and amateur music experiences felt more enthusiastic and extracted higher jazz appreciation from the concert than the ones with music education background. Marketing experts are advised to additionally explore these market groups. Indoor venue concert participants were shown to like this type of music festival as well as the selection of artists both at the specific venues and in the festival in general more than outdoor attendees. Finally, festival organizers could benefit from this study by acknowledging how the relationship between different visitors' profiles and festival setting influence behavior and the intellectual or emotional engagement in jazz performances.

3.7 Conclusions

This study aimed at exploring the audience experience as a part of a co-creative process within the organizational setting in the jazz festival context. To achieve this goal the Audience Experience Index (Radbourne et al., 2009; Radbourne et al., 2010) was applied as a performing art audience experience tool, adapted to the Spanish language and administered onsite at the 54th edition of the Heineken Jazzaldia festival in 2019 in San Sebastian, Basque Country, Spain. Through four indicators (Knowledge, Risk,

Authenticity and Collective Engagement) and familiarity with the festival setting, we analyzed how the items from the Index alter according to four corresponding objectives: admission (free versus paid) to concerts, the type of venue (indoor versus outdoor) of the concerts, the highest formal education degree obtained (Primary School, Secondary School, Bachelor's and Master or PhD degree) and the musical background of the participants (Music education and Professional/Amateur music experiences). Statistically significant differences were identified in each objective. In general, the research showed how audiences engage intellectually and emotionally with performances and the risk they take in regards to the festival setting (ticket price, program information, etc). This study offered new methodological insight as it applied the Audience Experience Index to a novel setting – the jazz festival. Additionally, it showed how jazz festival audiences interact and co-create their experiences during the concerts within the festival context. Therefore, this research contributes to event organizers in terms of their audiences' expectations and jazz experiences these seek and live.

We acknowledge the limitations of a convenience sample applied in this study and encourage greater sample representativeness in future research on jazz festival audiences. A specific challenge during the fieldwork was the festival context itself, which comprises a number of venues and concerts. Changing factors such as the weather (Oakes & Warnaby, 2011) challenge not only the festival program offer but also influence visitors' availability and accessibility for the research purposes.

Further research inquiry oriented toward anthropological-based research may offer a qualitative framework of jazz audiences' reflections and experiences to help understand the co-creation experience process and its possibilities in the jazz festival context.

Taking into account a great diversity of the festival's program, a comparison between the type of jazz/music offer in relation to festival setting and audience experience could enrich this knowledge area.

3.8 Acknowledgments

The authors are greatly thankful to the authors of the Audience Experience Index, especially Jennifer Radbourne who reviewed the adapted version of the questionnaire before its distribution at the jazz festival. The authors acknowledge a great support of the Professor Stephanie Pitts from the University of Sheffield who contributed with her observations and suggestions of the questionnaire. Moreover, we greatly acknowledge the support of Professor María Pilar Rodríguez and researcher June Calvo-Solaruze from the University of Deusto who revised the translation of the questionnaire from English to Spanish. We acknowledge a great support of PhD candidates from the University of Deusto - Rodoljub Jovanovic, who provided advice during the data analysis, and the fieldwork volunteers – Roberto Carlos Deras Melgar, Raquel Ortiz Ledesma, Maite Daniela Blanco Lococo, Davinia Gómez Sánchez, David Pérez Ortiz and Juliana Hernández Bertone. Finally, we are thankful to Heineken Jazzaldia Festival, especially its director Miguel Martín, for his help during the fieldwork and all the participants who were willing to take part in this research.

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